

THE ESSENCE AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY.

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Abstract: In this article, the issue of designing pedagogical technologies in the educational system is scientifically and theoretically analyzed.

Key words: Education system, science, technology, interest in learning, globalization era, national interests of each nation, each independent state, own culture, ancient values, native language, scientific and pedagogical experience, etc.

The political and economic development of the society is developed with the help of human thinking and intellectual potential. There are young people who demonstrate their talents and abilities in a certain direction of study and learning during their education in general secondary schools. Development of such ability, talent, intellectual potential is one of the main tasks of a modern educational institution. At this point, it should be acknowledged that under the leadership of the President of the Republic, a national model of the education system has been created in our country, which has not yet been found in the world experience. As a result of the care that is taken to educate in the spirit of loyalty to the ideas, to form independent and creative thinking skills for young people, the image of educational work has changed, updated, and efforts are being made to diversify the types of teaching in the educational process.

"... We always remember that the future of our country depends on how our young generation is educated, what spiritual qualities they grow up with, how active our children are in life, and what high goals they serve. It is necessary for us to always care and fight for their spiritual world, for their spiritual and moral maturity and physical health".

In order to fully ensure the spiritual, moral and physical development of young people, based on the requirements of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. ...fundamental reform of the field of education, ridding it of ideological views and prejudices from the past, raising it to the level of developed democratic states, a high moral and ethical system" (3.39), is being created and this based on the system, State educational standards were created for subjects in all educational institutions. At the same time, according to DTS, the educational system, content, and management should be changed and enriched in accordance with our national traditions, folk pedagogy, ancient history, culture, and noble values, and students' knowledge, skills, and qualifications should be improved. effective actions were taken on evaluation works in the rating system. Funds "Ulug'bek", "Republican children", "For a healthy generation", "Iste'dod" funds are active in order to encourage talented young people materially and morally and support their education abroad. is doing. It is clear that in the international political and economic spheres, there are great struggles around the issue of human resources. The main goal of this struggle is to use talented, intelligent, capable people who are masters of their profession and have excellent fundamental knowledge. In such conditions, it is necessary to pay attention to the education of people with such high spiritual potential, mainly young people, to correctly identify and reveal their abilities and talents, to reveal their intellectual potential, and to determine the criteria of spiritual maturity. It is one of the main tasks of school (secondary, secondary special, higher) education, to combine personal and social interests in learning, studying, social activities, labor processes, loyalty to the Motherland, fighting for the development of the Motherland.

Accordingly, at the same time as the practice of creating new textbooks, modern pedagogical and information technologies is brought to an end, it is appropriate to diversify the teaching technologies of general secondary, secondary special, and higher education schools in the teaching process. Based on this, we named the topic "Generalized pedagogical technologies of the teaching process" and we express our opinion on this basis.

At this point, it should be noted that the pedagogical process is a collaborative effort between the teacher and the student towards educational goals. Therefore, it is necessary for both the teacher and the student to know the different types of education and its essence in the process of education. After all, "... according to the slow or active participation of students in the educational process, the focus of education on memory or thinking, educational methods, tools, results - explanatory-demonstrative, problem-based, task-differential, programmed, divided into types such as algorithmized.

Thus, in the organization of the process of reading, teaching, learning, understanding, comprehension, conclusion, in the structure of educational information, in the use of educational methods and tools, and the results achieved under their influence, the generalized pedagogical technologies of the teaching process depending on the structure of the teacher-student activity - explanatory, problem-based, modular programmed, differential, individual, active, computerized, developmental education technologies can be distinguished.

Visual and explanatory educational technology. It is known that educational information is obtained in cooperation between teacher (teaching) and student (reading). Under the influence of both participants, the means of activity and the process of assimilation of knowledge are realized in psychological processes such as perception, understanding and comprehension, generalization, strengthening, and practical application. In the demonstration-explanatory type of education, they perceive, understand, consolidate and apply the essence of the information, things and events presented by the teacher to the student. This is one of the most widely used types of education in schools today. Visual-explanatory educational technology is a teaching technology focused on interpreting information using exhibitions.

If we interpret it from the point of view of the current period and the theory of pedagogy, with the help of demonstrations, new information is obtained by the student by looking at the exhibition, not in the "teacher-student" relationship, but in the "student-teacher" relationship. interpretation process. According to Professor O. Rozikov, demonstration-explanatory education is organized for children's memory. (p. 20,171). In demonstrative-explanatory education, the teacher explains the ready-made scientific conclusions in science using the method of explanation based on the exhibition, and analyzes it himself. Pupils listen to new concepts, perceive, understand, reinforce with the help of examples and learn how to apply them in practice. Learning new facts through experience, experimentation, and observation is carried out and summarized by the teacher. The more complex the new information, the more detailed the teacher explains. Acquired information, information and materials are realized with the help of operations that do not require creative activity. In this type of education, students develop attention, memory, and recall, but independent thinking is not formed. Thus, demonstrative-explanatory education is a learning activity aimed at students' perception, memorization, and recall of ready-made conclusions in science with the help of the teacher and based on his explanations, generalizations, and analyzes.

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